

Polarographic Analysis of the Hydrolysis of 2-Carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl Sulphide and 2-Carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl Sulphone in Aqueous Solution

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The formation and hydrolysis of Schiff bases and related compounds have been studied under different conditions¹. Schiff bases of substituted 2-carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl sulphide (I) and 2-carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl sulphone (II) associated with antitubercular activity² have been used in the present study.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of hydrolysis: Schiff bases in aqueous medium are hydrolysed¹ via the carbinol amine intermediate to an aldehyde and an amine.

The hydrolysis of Schiff bases of substituted 2-carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl sulphide (I) and 2-carboxy-4-aminodiphenyl sulphone (II) in aqueous buffer solution and in the pH range 0–14 at 30°, strictly follows first order kinetics and is irreversible.

R = H, Cl, CH₃, OCH₃
I, X = S
II, X = SO₂

Corresponding to the first order rate equation, the polarographic equation can be summarised as

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{i_{d0}}{i_d}$$

where i_{d0} is the y-intercept for the plot of $\log i_d$ vs t , and i_d is the diffusion current at any time t .

Half-wave potential: The value of $E_{1/2}$ is obtained from the intercept of the plot of E_{DME} vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$. Under the condition which precludes the hydrolysis of Schiff bases, except the Schiff base S₇, all bases showed a single diffusion wave ($E_{1/2} = 1.025$ – 1.260 V), whereas the Schiff base S₇ showed two diffusion waves ($E_{1/2} = 1.05, 1.335$ V).

Schiff bases are reduced at the DME in two subsequent stages as shown in Scheme 1.

X = S, SO₂
R = H, Cl, Br, OCH₃, NHCOCH₃, N(CH₃)₂
R' = H, Cl, CH₃, OCH₃

In the case of S_7 , the difference between the two values of $E_{1/2}$ is greater than 0.15 V, hence they are well separated from each other. ($1 \rightarrow 2$ and $2 \rightarrow 3$). Whereas with respect to the other Schiff bases, the difference between the values of $E_{1/2}$ is less than 0.15 V, hence they merge into a single diffusion wave ($1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3$). The diffusion wave which appears after the lapse of sometime, can be attributed to the electrolytic reduction of the electron-deficient carbon atom in the carbonyl group of the aldehyde (4) to the corresponding alcohol (5).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SUBSTITUTION OF COMPOUNDS 1 ($R' = H$) ON HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS

Compd no	X	R	$E_{1/2}$ V	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ (mV)
S_1	S	H	1 175	00
S_2	S	NHCOCH ₃	1 150	25
S_3	S	Br	1 125	50
S_4	S	Cl	1 150	20
S_5	S	CH ₃	1 210	-35
S_6	S	OCH ₃	1 250	-75
S_7	S	N(CH ₃) ₂	1 335	-160
S_{20}	SO ₂	H	1 005	170
S_{21}	SO ₂	Br	1 025	100
S_{22}	SO ₂	Cl	1 050	100
S_{23}	SO ₂	CH ₃	1 110	100

Electron-withdrawing groups, such as chloro, bromo and acetamido, when substituted in S_1 , are observed to increase the half-wave potential by 25–50 mV, whereas electron-donating groups, such as methyl, methoxy and *N,N*-dimethyl amino groups decrease by 35–160 mV (Table 1). The values of $E_{1/2}$ of Schiff bases S_1 , S_3 , S_4 and S_5 are decreased when they are converted into Schiff bases

S_{20} , S_{21} , S_{22} , and S_{23} respectively. This significant decrease by 100–170 mV is attributed to the presence of strong electron-withdrawing sulphonyl ($-\text{SO}_2-$) moiety in compounds S_{20} – S_{23} .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of G.R. (Merck) or AnalaR (B D.H.) grade. An Elico LI-120 pH meter with glass-calomel electrode and a Systronic 1632 polarograph were used. Kinetic measurements were performed at 30° in a thermostatic water-bath. Gelatin (0.02%, w/v) was used as the polarographic maxima suppressor. Interference of dissolved oxygen was eliminated by purging the sample with nitrogen.

Polarograms of 23 Schiff bases (S_1 to S_{23}) were obtained and their characteristics studied in aqueous buffer solution under different conditions as given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Schiff base	Conditions		
	at $t = 0$	$t = 60$ min	$t = \alpha$
$S_1 - S_6$	One wave	Two waves	One wave
S_7	Two waves	Three waves	One wave
$S_8 - S_{23}$	One wave	Two waves	One wave
Identification of wave	Due to C=N	Due to C=N and C=O	Due to C=O

References

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